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THE CULT OF MOUNTAINS IN AZERBAIJANI FOLKLORE AND ITS SEMANTICS ASSOCIATED WITH THE CULT OF ANCESTORS

Abstract.

The article broadly reflects the Azerbaijani people's belief in the cult of mountains, their mythical worldview, and their beliefs and convictions regarding the sanctity of the mountain. The place and role of the cults of mountains have been discussed in the ancient tradition of epic poetry, in the creativity of ashugs, and in our bayatis. Belief in mountains has been explored in the epics "Oguz Khagan" and "Kitabi-Dede Korkut", and the place and status of mountains in our myths and legends. In early mythological thought, the mountain was the starting point of creation.

Keywords: *the cult of ancestors, ancestors, national value, Dede Korkut, the cult of mountains*

Introduction: Azerbaijani people have preserved the tradition of treating the sacred places of their ancestors as sacred spaces, passing it down from generation to generation, from century to century. Just as our ancestors revered and respected the four elements involved in creation—water, fire, wind, and earth—they also considered mountains as a divine space, a sacred place where the spirits of their ancestors resided. This idea is supported by a multitude of beliefs and the belief system that has developed among the people, as well as proverbs that have existed throughout history. Examples include: "The breath of the mountain is the breath of Isa," "The higher the mountain, the more it opens a path above," "The man with the mountain behind him has a heart of stone," "When winter comes to the mountain, troubles come to the brave," "The mountain supports the mountain," "Mountains don't meet, but people meet," "A mountain on top of a mountain," "The mountain signifies greatness, elevation," and "Even if you are a mountain, you seek shelter in the mountain." Sometimes, when people witness the joy or happiness of a loved one, they use expressions such as "My heart has turned into a mountain (One's heart is filled with proud of someone)," to indicate the grandeur and elevation of the mountain. Elchin Galib Oglu has described the mountain as a divine symbol in the minds of ancestors, emphasizing that "The Turkish god is the Turkish person."

It is not a coincidence that a bedridden patient sometimes desires the snow from the peak of a mountain and thinks of finding a balm for the illness from that snow. The snow on the mountains, being in high altitudes and in places where human feet have not touched, is pure and clean. For this very reason, it is considered a medicine for the patient."

"Our brave commanders, considering the mountain as a sacred repository, conducted their most important negotiations at the mountain's peak or in areas close to it, believing that the spirits of their ancestors roaming the mountains would assist them. In the past, when our grandmothers and young brides saw the mountain from a distance, their practice of covering their heads with a cloth was directly connected to this sacred tradition. Even the ancient people, who lived before our era, settled in caves at the foot of the mountain,

considering the mountain a place of refuge. In earlier times, fortresses built in the mountains to protect against enemies also reflect a direct belief in mountain worship."

Main text: Interestingly, in the ancient Altai epic, when describing the homeland of the khans, it was stated: "At the foot of the Black Mountain, Karat Khan lived. At the foot of the White Mountain, White Khan lived" (5, p. 306). In the "Dede Korkut" epic, there was a custom of lighting a bonfire on the mountain's peak during both joyful celebrations of the people and the sad days when the enemy attacked and devastated the land, calling for help to the village and the people. In our love epics, when the heroes found themselves in difficulty, they would consider the mountain a sacred ancestral place and ask for help from the mountain. Many have found their healing by considering the mountain spring as the water of life. In our Bayati poems and Ashiq songs, there are many references to faith in the mountain, reliance on the mountain, and opening secrets or addressing the mountain. Let's pay attention to a bayati (a traditional Azerbaijani folk quatrain) that is popular among the people::

Dağlar dağımdı mənim,
Sırr oylağımı mənim,
Ulular oyaq qalib,
Yaman çağımı mənim! (20)

*The mountains are my ruin,
The valley of my secrets.
The elders stay awake,
In my troubled time!*

As seen in the example, the mountains are portrayed as a symbol of sorrow, a partner of secrets, and an object of invocation. All these examples show that our ancestors viewed the mountains not only as a sacred place but also as a protector of lineage and clan, and as a sacred space for the spirits of their forefathers. The nearly 30 years during which the mountains, forests, and natural resources of our ancestral land, Karabakh, were plundered by foreign invaders were, in fact, the greatest blow to our people and our state. The declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Solidarity for the Green World" in our country is a valuable contribution to the preservation of these values. At the same time, it serves as a strong example of the enemy's intention to hinder

the establishment of a green, prosperous, and healthy society. From a modern perspective, the cult of mountains highlights the importance of greenery and health. Mythologically, it embodies strength, power, beauty, love, unity, and solidarity. Both perspectives are rooted in the prosperity, health, strength, invincibility, and resilience of the nation.

The Tuvan Turks hold ceremonies in honor of the cult of mountains by climbing the mountains. These ceremonies were not held at the peak of the mountains but at their foothills. Women would not ascend the mountains to worship them (6, p. 52), as they considered the mountains sacred, great, and lofty, and would become tearful upon seeing them.

According to Agayar Shukurov, the Turkic peoples of Siberia, including the Altai, considered the mountain as the root, origin, and helper of their families and lineages. The folklore texts associated with mountains such as Mount Qaf, Alviz, Goshgar, Murov, Agri, the Caucasus, and Hacha Baba Tufan in Azerbaijani mythology are key indicators of this belief.

The author notes that, "according to ancient Turkic peoples, the mountain, like the tree, is a protector, a father, a mother; it is a spirit that protects the country, grants bravery, wisdom, and wholeness. The mountain has been a fortress that safeguards the people" (21, p. 54-55). Therefore, like the tree, which is one of the elements of nature, the mountain is also a symbol of creation. God, at the mountain's peak, creates 9 nations from the branches of the World Tree and scatters them across the 9 corners of the Earth. This indicates that in the early origins of the ancestors (before Islam), the elements that symbolized life—such as water (the source of life), the tree (the root of lineage), and the mountain (the symbol of invincibility, strength, and resilience)—played a significant role. Later on, these three elements became symbols of the strength, power, trust, and refuge of the great ancestors.

Mireli Seidov notes that, "the mountain is the spirit that protects the country, grants bravery, wisdom, and unity, and serves as a fortress that protects the people. The belief that the mountain's stones bring happiness and protect the homeland has always been held by our people. This is why the concept of the mountain cult emerged" (18, p. 264).

Even the stone, as a part of the mountain, is related to the ancient Turkic mountain cult that existed in the folk etymology before Islam. "If someone hears the sound of thunder for the first time in spring and picks up a heavy stone from the ground, raises it, and says, 'Oh Allah, may the heaviness of the sky bring abundance to me,' that year the household will have an abundant harvest." Or, "Facing the mountain, they would say, 'Oh my Lord, may the heaviness of the mountain bring abundance to my people.'" (14)

In many epics, such as Bilgamish, Kitabi- Dede Korkut, Koroglu, and others, heroes facing difficulties seek solutions by turning to the mountain, pouring out their troubles and words to it, and asking for help from the spirits of their ancestors who dwell in the mountains. In the creation epic of the Goyturks, Ergenekon, as well as in the common Turkic epic Oghuz Khagan and other epics like Kitabi-Dede Korkut and Koroglu,

Turkic heroes choose mountains as their place of residence. In the Koroglu epic, following the advice of his wise and worldly father, Ali, Rovshan chooses the mountainous, rocky land of Chanlibel as his eternal home. By drinking the water from the mountain spring of Koshabulaq, he gains strength in his arms, power in his voice, and sharpness in his words. It is this very spring that gives Koroglu his power and identity.

In the examples of oral folk literature, traces of mountain worship and the mountain cult can be found. In sacred sayings related to the mountain, proverbs, and even in the beliefs themselves, the mountain is often viewed as a symbol of elevation and greatness.

Dağ da olsan dağa daldalan. (Even if you are a mountain, seek shelter in the mountain.)

Dağ başında qar olar, ər kişidə ar olar. (There is snow on the mountaintop, and honor in a man.)

Dağ dağa arxadır. (The mountain supports the mountain.)

Dağ dediyin ucalıqdır, ucalıq. (A mountain is elevation, pure elevation.)

Dağ nə qədər uca olsa, el üstündən yol salar. (No matter how high a mountain is, it will open a path over it.)

Dağı dağ üstə qoyub. (Moved the mountains.)

Dağlar nə qədər uca olsa, üstündən yollar aşar. (No matter how high the mountains are, paths will cross over them.)

Dağlar yalan götürməz. (Mountains do not deceive.)

Dağı daşdan, kişini başdan tanı. (You recognize a mountain by its stone, and a man by his head.)

Dağlarda sakin olan şəxs ümitsiz qayıtmaz. (A person dwelling in the mountains never returns hopeless.)

Nə dərdin var dağa de. (Whatever your pain, tell the mountain.)

Dağda dolaşana əcdad ruhu köməyində durar. (The spirit of the ancestors assists those who wander in the mountains.)

Sometimes, among the people, those who are in trouble, are referred to as having a "chest as heavy as a mountain." When someone is hurt by harsh words or attacked at their weak point, we say, "Oh, I struck their chest like a mountain." When giving a lesson to someone who does not know their place, we say, "We gave them a lesson." Among the people, when someone sighs in pain, we say, "May your sighs reach the mountains and stones," believing that by passing their pain and sorrow to the mountains, they will feel lighter. Similarly, expressions like "If I tell my sorrow to the mountain, it will melt," "I stand behind you like a mountain," and so on, are still common today. When someone builds a home through their own labor and effort, people say, "Look, he is a true man. A good son does not covet his father's wealth, but the true man works for himself and his family, striving through honest labor, placing mountain upon mountain with the callouses of his hands." Here, a person's hard work and strength are compared to the vastness and power of the mountain. From these examples, it is clear that the meanings of greatness, elevation, beauty, and greenery represented by the mountain are present not only in our oral folk

literature but also in written literature. The mountain is also a symbol of national unity, justice, strength, invincibility, and integrity.

Folklorist Rovshan Ali-zadeh, in the chapter "Beliefs Related to the Mountain Cult" of his monograph *Nature Cults in Azerbaijani Folklore*, notes that the mountain cult stands out among the cults of inanimate nature objects and related beliefs in Azerbaijani folklore. The author emphasizes that in our myths and legends, the mountain is often depicted in the forms of a mother, a wise old man, a hero, and so on. He also suggests that the idea of the early ancestors having a celestial origin is connected to their association with the mountain.

In his opinion, "In the early cosmogony, the creators are the great ancestors. According to cult beliefs, the mountain itself is the creative origin. This is clearly confirmed in the Oghuz Kagan epic. One of Oghuz's sons is named Dagh Khan. One of the twenty-four Oghuz tribes is descended from Dagh Khan. Thus, Dagh (Khan) directly participates in the cosmogonic origin of the Oghuz ethnos. In this case, the Oghuzs descended from Dagh Khan represent the 'created' group in the second phase of the cosmogonic creation process" (8, p. 23).

In the Turkic belief system, the mountain often plays the role of both a father and a mother. In Azerbaijani folklore, the association of mountain with elevation, the sky, and strength has granted it the function of a Father. In the early myths, there are accounts of the sky and the earth originally being one, and then later separating. Depending on the context, the mountain is sometimes associated with the earth and sometimes with the sky. This, in turn, causes the mountain to appear both as a mother and a father. However, this does not in any way negate its role as an ancestral father. In the *Kitabi-Dede Korkut* epic, we find that the Oghuz take their strength from the mountain, viewing it as a place of mystery and elevation.

In the *Kitabi-Dede Korkut* epic, after returning from captivity, Beyrek asks his sister:

Qarşu yatan qara tağı,
Sorar olsam, yaylaq kimün?
Bacısı isə cavabında söyləyir:
Qarşu yatan qara tağı sorar olsan,
Ağam Beyrəğin yaylasıydı (11, s. 61).

The one who sleeps across from the black mountain,

If I ask, what is the summer pasture?

His sister replies:

If you ask about the black mountain across from

us

It would be Lord Beyrek's summer pasture.

In the epic, when Salur Kazan learns that his son has been captured, he says:

"My Black Mountain is high, my son." The representation of mountains as symbols of elevation is directly related to their portrayal as mythical ancestors.

In *Dede Korkut*, the fact that the Oghuz women could communicate with the mountains and gain wisdom from them indicates the masculine origin of the mountain.

Thus, the study of beliefs related to the mountain cult reveals that the reverence for the mountain and its deification have left significant traces in Azerbaijani folklore. In the early mythological worldview, the mountain was a central element at the beginning of creation.

The frequent use of the phrase "The mountains of the great" in Bayatis, along with the idea that our ancestors shared their troubles with the great mountains, stems from a deep belief in the spirit of the ancestors.

A dağlar, ulu dağlar,
Çeşməli, sulu dağlar...
Şuşada bir iyid öldü.
Dağ kişnər, bulud ağlar! (16)
Oh mountains, great mountains,
Mountains with springs, mountains with water...
A brave man died in Shusha
The mountain neighs, the cloud cries!

The idea of the world being governed by the mountain. The mythical model of this idea, recorded in the 12th century in *Munisname*, shows that the belief in the World Mountain was very strong among Azerbaijanis. The tradition of starting a series of popular bayatis with references to the mountains (e.g., "Oh mountains, great mountains..."), and people sharing their troubles with the great mountains, stems from this belief (12, p. 14).

This bayati reflects the belief that the mountain is a sacred place. In some of our epics, when a hero encounters obstacles, he curses the mountains in frustration: "May the water dry up, may the trees wither, may the wolves and birds perish." The mountain, without its trees and water, cannot be alive. After such words, the mountain's slopes intervene to stop the storm and illuminate the hero's path. This is because mountains, like the living, are not dead without water and trees.

The plots in ancient world cultures are often associated with the names of only a few individuals, such as Gilgamesh, Oghuz Khan, Alexander the Great (*Zulqarnayn*), and others (3, p. 105). In the *Asli-Kerem* epic, Kerem curses the mountain and the black forest. His mentor, Lala, forbids him from repeating those words. He says, "Boy, do not speak such words, do not curse, for curses have two sides" (9, p. 75-78). Lala's advice to Kerem reveals that the mountain and forest, symbols of greenery, beauty, and sanctity, should not be cursed. This is because the spirits of the ancestors reside there.

Xarab qalmış Ərzurumun dağları,
Bir yol aşıb gedir sənin belinnən.

Ağzım açım, sənə qarğış eliyim,
Qəbul olsun hər nə çıxsa dilimnən.
The mountains of ruined Erzurum,
A path crosses, going from your back.

If I open my mouth, may I curse you,
May whatever comes from my lips be accepted.

Ramazan Qafarlı notes that one of the earliest natural beings worshipped and deified by the Turks is the mountain. Due to its proximity to the Sky God, the mountain was sanctified in the imagination of the ancestors and was considered the main link that connected

people to the Creator. According to ancient Turkic belief, the World Mountain consists of three layers: the first layer is Altundag, located at the intersection of nine climates, with its peak reaching the sun; the second layer is Demirdag (also called Temirtav or Tomurtav), which is located on the earth's surface, in the depth of nine forests; the third layer is Bakirdağ, which is located in the dark realm where the nine seas of the underworld converge. Demirdag was said to rise up to the 12th layer of the sky. From this perspective, the place we call a mountain, its peak, is also considered a sacred space (13, pp. 327-330).

If we pay attention to the works of Azerbaijani ashiks, we can see that all master craftsmen have written couplets that begin with a reference to the mountain:

Xəstə üçün təpəsində qar olur,
Hər cür çiçək açır, lələzar olur,
Çəşməsindən abi-həyat car olur,
Dağdır möhnəti, məlalı dağlar! (22)

On the mountain's peak, there is snow,

Every kind of flower blooms, it turns into a meadow,

From its spring, the waters of life flow

The mountains remove the burden, the sorrow of the soul!

The snow on the mountain peaks is unlike any other snow. Among the people, it is said that for someone who falls ill and lies in bed during the summer, "the snow from the mountain peak is needed." The snow from the mountain peaks in the summer is considered a remedy for the sick. This is because the mountain peak is close to the sky, to God, it is the highest of the high and a sacred place. The spirits of the ancestors roam the mountain peaks. It is for this reason that the snow on the mountain peak, where the spirits of the ancestors' feet have touched and their breath has lingered, creates a miracle. It becomes a balm for the soul of a person on their deathbed. Similarly, the icy water from the mountain spring is believed to heal the sick. It is said that it is the mountain water that grants immortality and invisibility to Khızır.

As Jalal Beydili notes, the Water of Life is a legendary water that is believed to grant immortality to those who drink it. The Water of Life, and the quest for eternal and infinite life in general, appear in many tales and myths.

In the folklore, it is said, "Respect the mountain as you would your father, greet the mountain's slope so that it does not get angry with you."

Once, a shepherd was grazing his animals at the foot of Mount Ağı. At noon, he saw that both he and his flock were dying of thirst. There was no water anywhere. He prayed to God, asking for a spring to appear and promised to sacrifice seven sheep. Suddenly, a spring appeared before him, and both he and his flock drank from it. He then thought to himself, "Why sacrifice seven animals for just one water? I am not mad!" He took seven pithe (a type of small animal), killed them, and said, "These are God's seven sacrifices." At that moment, the shepherd and his flock turned into stone together. The stones at the foot of Mount Ağı remain from that time.

Huseyn Ismayilov emphasizes the sanctity of Mount Ağı, which represents the homeland suffering in the captivity of the Armenians. He states, "Mount Ağı is included in the list of initial religious and mythological values. The Armenians' desire to appropriate this value further proves their wild attitude toward all sacred values."

The value given to the mountain and its exaltation as a sacred and high place is a characteristic of the Azerbaijani people and, in general, of all Turkic nations. This is because the Turks regarded the mountain as a pure and sacred place, where the spirits of the ancestors dwelled. The mountain was considered the first ancestral abode. For many years, the mountains of our homeland, which were under Armenian captivity, remained a longed-for place for our people.

The ancient Chinese believed that mountains and hills protected them from evil spirits. When there were no hills or mountains nearby, the Chinese would build a Buddhist temple. This tall, cylindrical structure (a pagoda) would serve as a substitute for the mountain. They would also place models of five sacred mountains at the tombs of their emperors to prevent evil spirits from tormenting the deceased. Thus, in many cultures, the mountain was regarded as a sacred ancestor that protected people from harmful, malevolent spirits. The belief in the mountain, and viewing it as the root of one's lineage, linked Kazan to the mountain (18, p. 106). The concept of the mountain as a central factor in the creation of the world and humanity is reflected in the following folk verse:

Dağlar təzələndi,
Qar yağdı, təzələndi.
Nuh Peyğəmbər gəldi,
Dünya da təzələndi [16].

Mountains were renewed,
Snow fell, and they were renewed.
Prophet Noah came,
And the world was renewed.

Konul Bunyadzadeh notes that according to the history of religion, the mountains were the first place where God communicated with His prophets. Therefore, mountains have always been the first witnesses to the communication between God and humans.

The author further explains that in ancient beliefs and myths, the mountains were regarded as the gathering place of gods, and such locations were considered the center of the world and the universe. For instance, in Greek mythology, Zeus and his gods established their thrones on Mount Olympus, from where they passed judgments on human destiny. Prometheus, seeking to protect humans from the wrath of the gods and empower them to fight against Zeus, steals fire from that mountain. As punishment, some versions of the myth say that he is chained to the rocks of another mountain, which is often identified as the Caucasus Mountains (4, p. 11).

The concept of mountains being closely connected with lineage, roots, and the land itself emerges as a significant theme. In the myths about the creation of the world and humanity, we see that mountains, stones, and caves play a central role. Floods caused by rain bring

mud into the mountain caves. When the sun heats the mud and the wind solidifies it, humans come into being. First, a male figure named "Oh Father" appears, followed by a female figure, "Ayva." The children born from them represent the generations and tribes that emerge from that lineage. After the death of the parents, they are buried in a mountain cave, which becomes sacred and is revered as a shrine.

The mountain cave here symbolizes the union of the four elements—earth, water, fire, and air. These elements are central to the process of creation, and the cave becomes a sacred space where divine or ancestral spirits reside. The cave, as part of the mountain, symbolizes the connection between different realms: the heavens, the earthly world, and the underworld. Seyfeddin Rzasoy describes the mountain as a place that unites the sky, the earthly world, and the underworld, serving as a passage or a bridge between these realms (19, s. 58).

The concept of ancestors and homeland is indeed a fascinating one in many cultures, especially in Turkish folklore and mythology. In this context, the connection between the ancestral hero and the land—specifically the grave site or sacred resting place—holds great significance. The term "Land", as used in the Oghuz dialect, not only refers to a tribe or community but also carries a deeper meaning, denoting a sacred space where the protective spirits of the tribe reside. This word encompasses the notion of a hill or mound, which serves as a symbolic marker of the location of ancestral spirits.

A number of researchers associated the concept of "ancestor-ancestor" with the existence of the state, its power, the heir to the land, property, the height-lineage, and the sacral force that keeps eli alive. They also emphasized that it is associated with the meaning of "father". There is an opinion that the land and everything on the land belongs to the Kagan. The ancient Turks, as well as the Azerbaijani Turks, have always considered the land sacred and considered their ancestral hearth inviolable. According to a legend circulating among the Tatars, when Meteden asks for a piece of land, he is ready for war, citing the fact that there is a tomb of his ancestors there. (1, p. 162).

In the mythical worldview of each of the Azerbaijani Turks, the mountain was considered as the great-grandfather, as the beginning of the roots and as the basis. The sky god was originally regarded as the ancestor. Also in Turkic peoples Oghuz is also the son of Goy, considered the first human ancestor, the Kagan of the Turkic state of Jahan. It was with his name that many genealogies were associated. As the first ancestor, sometimes the triad of Mountain, Tree and water acts as the main factor.

Since the mountain is sacred, Protective, the ancient Turks chose the mountains as their place of residence, refuge, and held their most business meetings on the top of the mountains. The fact that the world tree (tree of life), which unites 3 worlds into one, ends in the bosom of the mountain, and its roots extend into the underworld, has been likened to the human race, the root of which has also been likened. This similarity has also earned the tree of life model the status of a descendant,

a root tree. Shuvules symbolizing the World Tree were mentioned in Oguz Khan's epic. We coincide in the studies of Rodlov, Agayar Shukurov, Khalig Koroglu, S. Rzasoy and others. In our regions, brides who considered the mountain to be their father, grandfather and great ancestors covered it with the tip of the kalaghayi and gulvangi, which they tied their faces on their heads as a sign of respect. The interesting thing here is that the mountains are close to the heavens, pure and invincibility is also noticeable as an attribute of the Alps. It is no coincidence that, according to ancient mythological thought, Oguz Khan was called the son of God – Heaven, indicating his invincibility, alpinism, wealth, domination, as well as being a wise tribal leader. The same idea can be attributed to Dede Korkut, Gazan Khan, Koroglu, which is a transformative derivative of Oghuz Khan. Sometimes we have mythologists who introduce the celestial God himself as the first ancestor. For example, in the article "Shummer and the cult of the sun in Turkish folklore" Islam Sadig described God as the first ancestor. He also shows the sun, the sky as the first ancestor. "Turk is the son of God, God is the son of the Turk," he says (10).

Other factor that stands out here is the fact that the names of mountains, caves, trees and water are double-mentioned in mythological texts. At the top of the mountain there is water of vitality, at the foot of the mountain there are caves where ancient people lived, etc.

It means that the tree that grows on the mountain, by the water, is a symbol of creativity for him. The cave is the sacral space where the foundation of the formation was laid.

God creates 9 peoples from the branches of the world tree and scatters them on 9 sides of the world. So, in the creation of the ancestor at the very beginning (before Islam), the presence of water, which is the source of life, life, a tree and a mountain, which is a symbol of invincibility, fortitude, and wealth, is noticeable. Later, these three factors became the strength, strength, confidence and refuge of the great ancestor, and the place of the oath.

It is interesting that the mountain, which plays a role in the first human beginning, is a symbol of invincibility, a branched tree with arms, a symbol of strength, life, a ray of the sun, which replaces the male beginning of beauty in the bright world, a gray wolf, symbolizing war, strength, faith and struggle, is known from folklore texts. So the main thing here is that the gray wolf settled in himself the power of war and struggle, taking it from the mountain.

There are few who sometimes consider the sacred mountain as the main factor underlying its main beginning. Fuzuli Bayat, who is among our scientists who consider the mountain to be the mother, notes: "The Mountain is a mythological attribute of the mother of the Earth" (2, p. 154). From our archaic myths in the pre-Islamic worldview, there are very few texts that have come down to us today and are not subject to transformation, able to preserve their main root. Most of them have almost completely changed the form and initial version of culture as a result of the intervention of religion. In general, it should be emphasized that the

first man-man of the Azerbaijani people is considered the first creator of the cult.

In the broad sense of a society, a people has always been a leader, an elder, as well as a hero-man, father or ancestor who gave reason to society and guided it. What we call ancestor father here is also the hero of land, a confident person who has earned a name. From this point of view, when we look back on the past, our ancestors and forefathers drew attention from the point of view of their brave ancestors, heroic qualities, the embodiment of the worldview of the Azerbaijani Turks.

In the epic "Ergenekon" it was the gray wolf that showed the way to get out of the territory where the Turks lived for centuries, then it was the blacksmith who melted the high mountain and pulled them out of that hole. The blacksmith ensures the survival of the first ancestors in proper order. It gives them the equipment they need to survive.

In the "Ergenekon" epic, we encounter several types of cultural heroes. In one version, the Turks, who had multiplied and increased in the mountainous land of Ergenekon, sought to leave and reclaim their ancestral lands and territories. One of them, a blacksmith, announces that there is iron in the mountains. He suggests that by heating the iron with wood and coal, they will be able to melt it, which will allow them to escape the area. Here, we see the image of the mountain standing at the foundation of creation and origin.

"Ulu Khan went hunting with his retinue. He wished to establish a new homeland. With his companions, he cried out in a loud voice, and they reached the foot of a mountain. They came across a large plain. One of the people from Ulu Khan's retinue, the Kipchak Khan, said, 'Settle here. Let your descendants earn fame in these lands, ride horses, wield swords, and be like mountains in the eyes of your enemies.' After saying this, Ulu Khan continued on his journey. As evening fell, they got lost in the mountain paths and couldn't find their way. Then they saw two eyes shining from a distance. A gray wolf, as if signaling them to follow, guided Ulu Khan and his retinue down a bright path, leading them far ahead. It was only when the sky began to clear that Ulu Khan found the place he sought, thanks to the wolf. From then on, wherever Ulu Khan went, he would always see the gray wolf ahead. From that time, the wolf was considered a savior. You may even see, in rural areas of India, where people hang a wolf's head at the door to protect against the evil eye. They revered its strength, magic, and the power of its teeth, and some people even wear amulets with beads in their necks for protection.

One day, Oghuz Khan went hunting. Suddenly, he saw a girl sitting on the branch of a giant oak tree at the foot of the mountain. She was sitting on the branch of a pair of oak trees that grew at the base of the mountain, with blue eyes and a pleasant face—clearly a divine gift sent by God. Oghuz Khan took her as his wife, and they had seven sons. The Azerbaijani Turks of India are said to be descended from them. My grandfather used to say that in many regions of Azerbaijan – in Nakhchivan, Ganja, and Karabakh – there were places named "Kurtlar Mahallesi" (Wolf's Quarter) and "Kurtlar Meydanı" (Wolf's Square). As can be seen from the

text, the location where the event took place is connected to the mountain.

As in Turkish culture, in Azerbaijani folklore, mountains are given special significance (due to the belief that the souls of ancestors live in the mountains). Historically, our forefathers and saints have chosen the foothills of the mountains as sacred and ritualistic spaces. "In the Uyghur Turks' legends about Creation and Migration, the destruction of the Sacred Mountain, Kutluq, which they called the Mountain of the Sky Spirits, by enemies weakened the Uyghur state, and a series of calamities befell the land. After this disaster, the Uyghurs were forced to migrate from their homeland" (17, p. 217). It is interesting that the destruction of the mountain and the subsequent disaster that befell the Uyghur people symbolized their failure to protect the sacred land left to them by their ancestors. As in the case of Turkish peoples, there is a strong connection between the homeland and the spirits of ancestors. Kubra Yıldız Altun also believes that without the spirit of the earth, the soil has no power. From this perspective, in Turkish culture, the universe is thought of in a similar way to a human being. "Just as it is the spirit that keeps a person together, the creative force that holds the universe together is kut (sacred power) or a spirit-like structure." The author concludes that in Turkish culture, there is a link between the concepts of "Ancestral Homeland" and "Homeland" (7, p. 163). In Turkish lands, as well as in several regions of Azerbaijan, mountains and rivers are given sacred names, such as Khan Araz, Deli Kur (meaning "brave, hero, waterfall"), the Greater Caucasus, Baba Mountain, Agridag, and others. This naming tradition reflects the connection between the mountains and the cult of creation and ancestors. In the ancient belief system, it was thought that each tribe had its own sacred mountain, animal, or tree. These mountains were considered both sacred and as paternal figures. The Azerbaijani people also revered the mountains as sacred because the graves of their ancestors were located at the mountain peaks, and those places were always considered sacred sites where people would go to pray and seek blessings. "The belief in the sanctity of the homeland is also closely related to the belief in land and water," as some scholars argue (7, p. 393). In ancient Turkic traditions, great and renowned men were buried on mountaintops in the belief that this would bring them closer to God. There is a widespread belief in the concept of "ancestral mountain" in the folk culture. The author also suggests that the term "homeland" can be understood within the framework of the cult of the wise and patient woman or the paternal cult (7, p. 394). One of the symbols of ancestor worship is the sacred homeland and the sacred hearth. In fact, the tradition of lighting bonfires in our regions today is a reflection of respect for the spirits of our forefathers.

Interestingly, one of Oghuz's three sons is named Dag (Mountain). The descendants of these three brothers are known as the Uchoklar. Both the Bozok and Uchok tribes are part of the Azerbaijani Turks' lineage.

Conclusion: Therefore, we have tried to focus on several aspects related to the mountain cult. When it comes to the ancestral aspects of the mountain cult, it

becomes clear that the concept of origin and creation is valued in Azerbaijani myths in the following way:

- The cult of mountains is a fundamental and primary factor in the creation of the world and humanity.
- In the creation of the first ancestor, along with tree, water, and soil, the elements of mountain and cave are also present.
- The mountain stands at the beginning of the lineage.
- The mountain is the embodiment of respect.
- In many cultures, the mountain was considered a sacred ancestor.
- The mountain plays a central role in the creation of the world and humanity.
- The mountain is considered a sacred space where the spirit of the ancestors dwells.
- The mountain is part of the initial religious-mythological values.
- Mountains were the place where God first spoke to His prophets.
- Therefore, mountains are always the first witnesses of the communication between God and humans.
- The mountain was considered the center of the world and the universe.
- The spirit of the mountain, the mountain's soul, was considered the protector spirit of the clan and the ancestor.

The declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Solidarity for a Green World" in our country is significant in several aspects. One of the future priorities has been set as being a country with a clean environment and green growth. The mountain, as a symbol of purity, cleanliness, and greenery, has a great impact on the health of the environment and the protection of living beings. Protecting the mountains, which symbolize greenery, solidarity, and life, should become a moral duty for everyone.

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